

3D BIOPRINTING TECHNOLOGIES FOR SCAFFOLDS AND ADAPTING SIMPLE 3D PRINTERS TO LOW-COST 3D BIOPRINTER

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Abstract: *3D printing techniques are becoming state-of the art technique in the field of engineering research, enabling for the rapid and low-cost creation of prototypes and components using computer-aided design (CAD). In addition, interest to 3D printed scaffolds is also increasing in using these techniques in a clinical setting to create anatomically 3D printed models from medical imaging for research, training, and teaching. We discuss the benefits of common features of 3D bioprinting techniques, methods and 3D printed scaffolds for, healthcare professional education, in this article. We also try to explain how we can use simple 3D printer as bioprinter, that we can use it for printing scaffolds with changing some parameters of simple 3D printer. We preferred to use "Duplicator i3 Mini" 3D printer for the beginning. At the same time, we offer hard filament making method for extruder 3D bioprinters in this paper. We hope this knowledge will be of use to researchers, teachers, and students with little or no previous experience in 3D printing scaffolds processing who have identified a potential application for 3D printing in a medical context, or those with a more general interest in the techniques.*

Key words: *3D bioprinting, 3D bioprinting methods, 3D bioprinters, scaffolds, 3D printer, bio inks and bone tissues.*

Introduction.

Scaffolds. Scaffolds are substances which have been engineered to medical purposes proper cell interactions to make a contribution to the formation of recent practical tissues for scientific purposes. Cells are often 'seeded' into those systems able to be helping third-dimensional tissue formation [1].

Bone Scaffolds should serve 3 capabilities in tissue engineering applications. Firstly, are corporal parameters which require to identify the geometrical shape of the scaffold in particular its pore size and porosity. Second

required parameter is to provide sufficient mechanical strength. Finally last parameter is to allow the cell implantation and at the same time biodegradation rate of the scaffold. These parameters are illustrated in Fig.1

Fig.1. Required parameters for scaffolds.

Scaffold can be modeled using some architectural structures like honey-comb structure, circular, rectangular or gyroid structure. But we do not have to forget that, if architectures changed, pore size and porosity is also changed. Required pore size and porosity needs to be maintained as it disturbs scaffold's mechanical parameters. At the time pore size and porosity responsible for flow of nutrients and growth factors of bone. Kelvin architecture is taken into consideration as an open cellular structure, and it is used to model the scaffold mainly due to its resemblance to cancellous or spongy bone [2]

3D bioprinting has been a prospectively technique to make biomedical scaffolds for different hard tissue engineering applications due to good controllability over structural features such as porosity, pore size, and pore interconnectivity. Several 3D bioprinting techniques, extrusion-based 3D printing has been the most commonly preferred technique to fabricate tissue-engineered scaffolds given it allows usage of huge range of materials with different viscosities. Having the natural characteristics of bone tissue does not allow always directly to fabricate artificial bone, because of bone tissue regeneration and due to the relatively complex structure of bone [3].

Choosing the most optimal material is considered one of the most priority aspect during the 3D bioprinting process. When materials are implanted, they have a biological response into the body. Many of them are poisonous to the body, whereas others are biocompatible (not toxic). Biocompatible materials are divided into three categories: bioinert, resorbable, and bioactive. But in this article, we decide that we do

not discuss about categories of biomaterials. Instead of this we focused on the state-of-the-art 3D bioprinting methods for scaffolds [4].

It is not secret now that the cost of bioprinters is so high that, accordingly, this problem prevents them from performing new experiments. Sometime researcher can not by new bioprinter due to this problem. Now we are working to solve problem by learning types of bioprinters and by doing analysis working processes and software parts of them. Later our team will try to explain our initial results depended on the issue. In our view, fabricating bionics or filaments to bioprinters is considered one of the unexpected, and painful point, which is required urgent solution. During the reading the article you may see the some fundamental experiments and feedbacks focused on making new budget filament machine.

2. Materials and Methods.

Evolution and classification of 3D bioprinting

2.1. Evolution of 3D bioprinting

A few years ago, it was not quite realistic to achieve 3D bioprinting of perfectly functional artificial organs for implantation. But nowadays, we cannot denied that bioprinting techniques have evolved significantly. It will be good if evolution way of three-dimensional bioprinting is looked in.

In 1984, Charles Hull invented stereolithography (SLA) for printing 3D objects from digital data, it was a first step and symbol the birth of 3D printing. [5]. Bioprinting was first demonstrated in 1988 while Klebe using a standard Hewlett-Packard (HP) inkjet printer to deposit cells by cytoscribing technology [6]. In 1996, Forgacs and co-workers drew a conclusion that apparent tissue surface tension was the macroscopic manifestation of molecular adhesion between cells and provided a quantitative measure for tissue cohesion [7]. In 1999, Odde and Renn first utilized laser assisted bioprinting to deposit living cells for developing analogs with complex anatomy [8]. In 2001, direct printing of a scaffold in the shape of a bladder and seeding of human cells took place [9]. In 2002, the first extrusion-based bioprinting technology was reported by Landers et al., which was later commercialized as "3D-Bioplotter" [10]. Wilson and Boland developed the first inkjet bioprinter in 2003 by modifying an HP standard inkjet printer [11]. A year after, their team implemented cell-loaded bioprinting with a commercial SLA printer [12]. In the same year, 3D tissue with only cells (no scaffold) was developed. In 2006, electrohydrodynamic jetting was applied to deposit living cells [13]. Scaffold-free vascular tissue was engineered through bioprinting by Norotte et al. in 2009 [14]. In 2012, in situ bioprinting was attempted by Skardal et al. on mouse models [15]. The following years saw the introduction of many new bioprinting products, such as articular cartilage and artificial liver in 2012, tissue integration with circulatory system in 2014 and so on [16,17]. In 2015, coaxial technology was adopted by Gao et al. for fabrication of tubular structure [18]. In 2016, Pyo et al. applied rapid continuous optical 3D printing based on DLP [19]. In the same year, cartilage model

was manufactured by Anthony Atala’s research group using integrated tissue-organ printer (ITOP) [20]. In 2019, Noor et al. succeeded in manufacturing a perusable scale-down heart [21]. And a few months later, bioprinting of collagen human hearts at various scales based on freeform reversible embedding of suspended hydrogels (FRESH) technology was achieved by Lee et al [22]. A timeline for the evolution of bioprinting technology up to state-of-the-art is given in Table.1.

Table.1. A brief history of bioprinting

In years	1980	In years	1990	In years	2000	In years	2010	In year	2019
	1984, SLA was invented representing the birth of 3D printing.		1996, cell sticking together during embryonic development was observed.		2001, 3D printed synthetic scaffold for human ladder was achieved.		2012, <i>in situ</i> bioprinting was realized on animals.		2019, cardioid structure was first bioprinted in Tel Aviv University: collagen human heart at various scales was engineered using FRESH technology.
	1988, bioprinting was first demonstrated by 2D micro- positioning of cells		1999, first use of laser technology demonstrating 2D patterning of living cells was reported.		2002, first extrusion- based bioprinter was used and further commercialized as “3D Bioplotter”		2015, tubular structure was printed by coaxial technology.		
					2003, first inkjet bioprinter was developed by modifying an HP standard		2016, rapid continuous optical 3D printing		

			inkjet printer. 2004, 3D tissues with only cells (no scaffolds) was presented. 2009, scaffold-free vascular constructs were fabricated.	based on DLP was applied: cartilage model was obtained by ITOP system.	
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2.2. Classification of 3D bioprinting

2.2.1 3D Modeling

The 3D printing process requires a 3D model of object to be printed. The model can be obtained by using many different computer-aided design (CAD) programs, as well as 3D scanning system (optical, MRI, CT or imagen based). More efficient printing results can be achieved if design is made by taking into consideration the technology and sensitivity of the 3D printer [23].

Generally, a 3D bioprinting process consists of five steps.

- (i) Obtaining the 3D model of the target object in the digital environment
- (ii) Converting the model file of the desired object into a digital file format compatible with 3D printer such as STL.
- (iii) Slicing the model into layers by means of a 3D printer slicer software and producing the G-codes.
- (iv) Transmission of the G-codes to the printer.
- (v) Printing the modeled object.

Fig.2 highlights data about 3D bioprinting processes

Fig.2 Stages of the manufacturing process by using 3D printing technology.

2.2.2 Stereolithography (SLA)

Stereolithography is an additive manufacturing process that, in its most common form, works by focusing an ultraviolet (UV) laser on to a vat of [photopolymer](#) resin. With the help of computer aided manufacturing or [computer-aided design](#) (CAM/CAD) software, the UV laser is used to draw a pre-programmed design or shape on to the surface of the photopolymer vat. Photopolymers are sensitive to ultraviolet light, so the resin is photochemically solidified and forms a single layer of the desired 3D object. Then, the build platform lowers one layer, and a blade recoats the top of the tank with resin. This process is repeated for each layer of the design until the 3D object is complete. Completed parts must be washed with a [solvent](#) to clean wet resin from their surfaces [24].

2.2.4 Digital Light Processing (DLP)

SLA and DLP technologies are very near to each other. They are differentiated by the source of the light to be used. In DLP printing technology we can see projector in the bottom of the resin pool instead of ultraviolet laser. In the SLA the laser beam scans the layer, while the projector in the DLP acts on the entire layer surface at the same time, resulting in faster print speeds. However, SLA is more suitable for the parts requiring high resolution [25].

2.2.5 Binder Jetting.

Binder Jetting is a family of additive manufacturing processes. In [Binder Jetting](#), a binder is selectively deposited onto the powder bed, bonding these areas together to form a solid part one layer at a time. The materials commonly used in Binder Jetting are metals, sand, and ceramics that come in a granular form.

Binder Jetting is used in various applications, including the fabrication of **full-color prototypes** (such as figurines), the production of **large sand casting cores and molds** and the manufacture of [low-cost 3D printed metal parts](#). [26]

2.2.6 Polyjet

PolyJet is a powerful 3D printing technology that produces smooth, accurate parts, prototypes and tooling. With microscopic layer resolution and accuracy down to 0.014 mm, it can produce thin walls and complex geometries using the widest range of materials available with any technology. Benefits of Polyjet: Create smooth, detailed prototypes that convey final-product aesthetics. Produce accurate molds, jigs, fixtures and other manufacturing tools. Achieve complex shapes, intricate details and delicate features. Incorporate the widest variety of colors and materials into a single model for unbeatable efficiency. [27]

2.2.7 Fused deposition modeling (FDM)

Fused Deposition Modeling (FDM) is a type of additive manufacturing technology that enables the construction of three-dimensional objects, prototypes and products through a computer-aided or driven manufacturing process. It is used in 3-D printing or the design of solid models and prototypes in a layered or additive approach. FDM is also known as fused filament fabrication or fused deposition method. Fused Deposition Modeling (FDM) is trademarked by Stratasys Inc., a leader in building FMD-based 3-D printers.

2.2.8 Selective Laser Sintering. (SLS)

Selective laser sintering (SLS) is an [additive manufacturing](#) (AM) technique that uses a [laser](#) as the power source to [sinter](#) powdered material (typically [nylon](#) or [polyamide](#)), aiming the laser [automatically](#) at points in space defined by a [3D model](#), binding the material together to create a solid structure. It is similar to [selective laser melting](#); the two are instantiations of the same concept but differ in technical details. SLS (as well as the other mentioned AM techniques) is a relatively new technology that so far has mainly been used for [rapid prototyping](#) and for [low-volume production](#) of component parts. Production roles are expanding as the [commercialization](#) of AM technology improves. [28]

2.2.9 Selective Laser Melting

Selective laser melting (SLM) is one of many proprietary names for a metal additive manufacturing technology that uses a bed of powder with a source of heat to create metal parts. Also known as direct metal laser melting (DMLM), the ASTM standard term is powder bed fusion (PBF). PBF is a rapid prototyping, [3D printing](#), or [additive manufacturing \(AM\)](#) technique designed to use a high power-density [laser](#) to melt and fuse metallic powders together. [29]

2.2.10 Electron Beam Melting (EBM)

Electron beam melting (EBM) is a type of [additive manufacturing](#) for metal parts. It is often classified as a rapid manufacturing method. The technology manufactures

parts by melting metal powder layer by layer with an EB in a high vacuum. Unlike some metal sintering techniques, the parts are fully dense, void free, and extremely strong. The vacuum environment in the EBM machine maintains the chemical composition of the material and provides an excellent environment for building parts with reactive materials such as [titanium alloys](#). [30]

3.Results and discussion.

3.1 Adapting simple 3D printers to a bioprinter.

In general, 3D bioprinting is based on the layer-by-layer precise positioning of biological constituents, biochemicals and living cells, by spatial control of the placement of functional constituents of the fabricated 3D structure. 3D bioprinting is based on three fundamental approaches: (i) biomimicry or biomimetics, (ii) autonomous self-assembly, and (iii) mini tissue building blocks, as described extensively elsewhere. [31]

Three dimensional (3D) bioprinting is a new interdisciplinary research field, which utilizes computer engineering, material science, robotics and biomedical engineering in order to provide novel applications in life sciences through tissue engineering and regenerative medicine [32]. It is therefore evident that widespread access to this new technology would benefit researchers in several different fields. However, current commercially available 3D bioprinters have a high cost (10,000–150,000\$) and low customization capacity, while they also require costly consumables and highly skilled staff for operation and maintenance, limiting their applicability. In this regard, many researchers have tried to develop low-cost 3D bioprinters based on different extrusion methods and materials [33]. However, a 3D custom made bioprinter that is open source, ultra-low cost and easy to set up and operate, along with an evaluation of its applications for developing models in stem cell research, has not yet been reported.

Above we have discussed about some problems which are the related to costs of

3D bioprinters. As a considered counted issues, we offer way making the low-cost bioprinters. In the first step most suitable extrude-based 3D printer was chosen by the comparison with 3D bioprinters. In the next step, software parts were analyzed at the same time some codes of 3D printer were changed. As we said in the introduction our option was “Duplicator i3 Mini” Fig.3 3D printer for the beginning. Fig.3. *Duplicator i3 Mini and its accessories*

Then hardware part was adapted to bioprinter by using CAD programs.

Fig.4 (a) 3D model of base, (b) and (c) technical drawing of adapted 3D bioprinter.

4. Conclusion

In this report, we provide detailed instructions for the modification of a commercial 3D printer into an ultra-low-cost 3D bioprinter by the learning doing deep analyzing classification of 3D printers. In introduction we try to share general information about scaffolds and required parameters for scaffolds. In this article you faced to our pyramid scheme for requirements for scaffolds. Evolution of 3D printing is also showed in detail in Table.1. The nine methods of three-dimensional printing are given in this work. Our observation by literature review showed that, Solidworks software versions, NX software versions were the most preferred software by the researchers who worked on this area. So we can advise to learn these software which is the counted above for who wants to continue his or her future scientific career in this field.

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